

1. Title and Details

a. Title

Faris' First Form of Faris' Theory of Reality

b. Author Information

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c. Note

(1) It is requested to please pay attention that complete Research team is needed because I am not only working on First Form of Reality but also on these things

1. Second to twelfth Form of Theory of Reality based on chains(second,third),multi-directions(fourth),Classifications(fifth),Basis(sixth),differentiations(seventh),types(eighth),versions(ninth),styles(tenth),orientations(eleventh),words(twelfth).

2. Quantum Variables can together and individually be arranged in tables or spectrums. Each or all quantum variable tables or spectrums cannot be explained by Quantum Theory, String Theory and Reality. As Degrees of Freedom for quantum variables increase these theories start to break down. Table is made for discrete arrangement, spectrum is made for continuous arrangement.

3. Working on concepts like "Descriptions"(better than Reality Theory Forms), "Folded Answerables"(better than Description), "Existences"(better than Folded Answerables) up to infinity these all infinite things together form a circular loop in which one can move from infinity and always reach same place. This circular loop can again be considered inside circular loop(that contains other infinite things in circle) up to infinity in this way. Understanding Whole system(infinity/infinity) will lead to indeterminate answer. Loop can have any shape instead of a circle only.

4. Classified science as Artificial Science(Theory of String Shapes means string can be bent to any shape comes under Artificial Science) and Real Science.

5. Existing Perspective of Science is based on "Velocity" but the best Perspective is "Information" because every perspective is Information.

(2)After looking on the internet i have realized that advancement in technology is very fast therefore it is possible that some of the concepts on which i am working may be discovered by any other person in near future so therefore i found it necessary to introduce these concepts first even in the rough form.Even some of my concepts or ideas(I am not mentioning that specific ideas) are available on internet because someone already get those ideas independently I think.There are a lot of ideas and concepts on internet which i also discovered independently.

(3) 1.Important announcement is that it is mentioned with my picture in 2025 Bahria Town School and College Yearbook that “Teamwork is important.Working with others has shown me how different ideas can come together,and that will help me in my career. ” Just to make things clear “This is not my statement”,although team work is good but there must be some misunderstanding about my ideas here because i get all of my Scientific Ideas and other Ideas Independently without anyone help and write Research articles without anyone help until now(05-June-2025).

2.This is not criticism but a clarification to avoid misunderstanding in public,I will request BTSC to change my statement if changed then it would be good otherwise i have made a clarification.Even If this statement represents observation of Respected Professors then i have already highlighted a mistake to avoid misunderstanding.

3. “I have clearly mentioned that I get all of my ideas independently. Whatever this statement is, it's most likely to be a misunderstanding”.

2.Short Summary

First I have presented a complete picture of Quantum Reality with Theory of Foreed Parts then i presented Theory of science to highlight Fundamental Subjects of Reality which are Math and Physics and told all other subjects can be derived by these two fundamental subjects.After this I told that Reality Theories are complex mathematically so this problem can be resolved by using ShortCut Quantities and Reality Theories must counter certain factors of Reality this can resolved by using MustAdd quantities.I made clarification that Math-Phy must be combinely used and therefore used words Math-Phy and science alternatively.Finally presented First Form of Reality Theory by three Faris' Theories.First Theory goes to -infinity or Foreed boundary(lower boundary or small quantum variables boundary),second goes to Mid of Reality or Faris Point which exist if Reality has upper and lower boundary and Third Theory describes +infinity or Verse boundary(upper boundary or big quantum variables boundary) of Reality.Faris' Field equation also called Faris' God Equation describes Local Part(which Is Scaled Part) and this equation can

also be generalized to other Parts(Non-Scale and Anti-Scale Parts).Faris Field' Equations predictions about fields and grids can be checked that whether they appear in reality or not by small and big light splits and then fission and fusion chain reactions can prove it practically if they appear. It is possible that there is upper boundary but not lower or there is lower boundary but not upper to resolve such problems a chain is informed in other higher forms of Reality Theories.One Quantum Variable called Quantum Structure is described as a Prove and Example of all content of this Research paper.Quantum structure is described because it includes existing Quantum Theory,String Theory and transforms to Relativity at Big Scale.

3.Keywords

- 1.Quantum Theory Changed
- 2.String Theory Proved
- 3.Science Subjects Combined
- 4.Relativity derived
- 5.Everything Theory Replaced
- 6.Reality Theory 1st-Form

4.Statements and Declarations

a.Competing Interests

No, I declare that the authors have no competing interests or other interests that might be perceived to influence the results and/or discussion reported in this paper.

b.Funding

No Funding

c.Author Contribution

I am Mirza Faris Ahmad .The only Author and Researcher of this Research Paper.

5.The Theory

a.Introduction

In order to describe the whole universe usually Theory of Everything is used which unifies all forces .But to describe whole Reality which includes not only universe but also all physical parallel universes and beyond them I am going to introduce Theory of Reality that describes whole Reality.

b.Headings

Let me introduce 5 things before detailed discussion

(1)Theory of Fored Parts

Introduction

Quantum Theory and String Theory describe Quantum System or Quantum Reality in a limited manner.

Explanation

Quantum System or Quantum Reality is divided into Parts. Each Part is extremely detailed.

Local Part

Inside Local Part, There is Reality lines, in each reality line there is levels, in each level there is quantum structures, in each quantum structure there is sub-quantum structures. Each Quantum Variable (Reality line is biggest quantum variable) is subset of bigger quantum variable. Problem is this that it can go to infinity because there can be infinite quantum variables so good thing is to use two numbers like n_1, n_2 where n_2 will describe which quantum variable number (example: Level is quantum variable but there are many levels as Level 1, Level 2 etc so Quantum Variable Number means level number here) is discussed and n_1 will describe which quantum variable (example: level is quantum variable) is discussed.

Quantum Variable

At every Scale there are different Quantum Variables. Scale refers to power of 10. As at 10^{-9} Scale there is one quantum variable which is subset of the quantum variable of 10^{-8} Scale. Quantum variable at 10^{-8} is same but its number called Quantum variable number can differ suppose level is quantum variable at 10^{-8} then there can be many levels like level 1, level 2.

Quantum Structures

1. Some Details

Measurement

Measurement means to get knowledge of physical quantities of a quantum system.

Methods of Measurement

Measurement can happen by Three Methods

i. Observation (Direct Approach)

Observation is that measurement method which involves the use of photons to get knowledge of physical quantities of a quantum system.

ii. Reference (Direct and Indirect Approach)

Reference is that measurement method which involves the use of references to get knowledge of physical quantities of a quantum system.

Example

If there is one quantum structure entangled to another and both quantum structures are being detected by the detector continuously then if someone observes one quantum structure the same change will appear in the other so the detector notices the change.

iii.Math (Indirect Approach)

Math is that measurement method which involves the use of mathematics and calculations to get knowledge of physical quantities of a quantum system.

Example

Uncertainty Principle is only because of Observation but mathematically it is entirely possible to predict all observables simultaneously.

2.Observational Quantum Structures

A Quantum Variable named quantum structure detected by the method of observation is called observational Quantum Structures.

i.Trap Quantum structure

The structure defined by Trap's Foundation is Trap quantum Structure.This Quantum Structure is explained by Theory of Trap.

Trap's Foundation

Electron-Quark Trap changes upon Observation-1 to Non-Sync Trap from the Sync one.

Observation-1

The Quark and Electrons are moving from one probability position to second probability position(quark in nucleus and electron in orbit) but because of Sync Trap electron and quark together moves from one probability position to second probability position which upon Observation-1 collapses to Non-Sync Trap because electron and quark now does not maintain same Trap,now distance between electron and quark changes and even quark and electron spin and orbit movement also goes out of sync.

ii.Probabilistic Quantum Structure

The structure defined by Probabilism's Foundation is Probabilistic quantum Structure.This Quantum Structure is explained by Theory of Probabilism.

Probabilism's Foundation

When Superposition state ' Ψ ' changes upon Observation-2 to the particle form or wave form depending on Observation-2 Types then this causes particles or strings to change their way of movement.

Observation-2

There are two types of Observation-2

Wave Observation-2

In Wave Observation-2 particles travel through the Dimensional Hole to all positions predicted by probability position function centered at all entangled points of One Entangled Structure orbit, The overlap in probability positions make electron(s) move.

Example

Use a vacuum tube with anode and cathode and they have positive and negative charge respectively now fill tube with hydrogen gas. Use a light source to illuminate cathode, electron will be emitted by photoelectric effect and move towards anode the electron of hydrogen atom excite now when they deexcite photon is emitted ,by the light of these photons one can observe electron moving in orbit in a stationary wave like shape through dimensional holes.

Particle Observation-2

In Particle Observation-2 electrons are forced at certain positions and then move in orbit.

Example

Using same experiment in previous example, When anyone observes an hydrogen atom through another light source then the particle in the atom gets a photon as energy and is forced at one specific position instead of travelling through Dimensional Holes to many probability positions and electron can be seen as moving in a circular orbit in Resultant Quantum Structure.

Superposition State

There is no thing like True Superposition, every superposition needs “Superposition Variable” or “Superposition Constant” or both to exist.

Equation

Ψ = Spacetime's Fluctuation make Dimensional Hole which makes particle to move to different positions

Ψ = Virtual Particle Fluctuating at different places

$\Psi = P(x,y,z)$

Example

In the case of an electron in orbit ,the electron is a particle found to be wave because of two Superposition Variables called Dimensional Hole and Entangled point.

iii. Transition Quantum Structure

The structure defined by Transition's Foundation is Transition quantum Structure. This Quantum Structure is explained by Theory of Transition.

Transition's Foundation

When electrons get energy to change state then upon Observation-3 it stops in between transition states and emits remaining energy.

Observation-3

When an electron changes orbit by getting energy from photon, upon Observation-3 it is stopped at some position between orbits then it radiates energy, this shows discrete energy states are true without Observation-3 because at that moment the electron is mostly at entangled point orbit but on Observation-3 electron can be anywhere even at low entangled probability positions present between two orbits where electron moves for changing orbit.

Combined Explanation

I have described a Quantum Variable called Quantum Structure and I have also described its all Quantum Variable Numbers. There are three Quantum Structures at the same scale. Quantum Variable is Quantum structure and Quantum Variable Number is 3. Quantum Structures together form Atom at this scale of Quantum Variable so quantum structure and atom means same thing. Atom is Probabilistic thing with Sync Trap and Discrete States which upon observation behaves in a way depending upon Observer's Observation.

Note

Quantum Structures are the most common type of quantum variable anyone can detect. When someone detects an atom depending upon the method of detection of the atom one can observe different quantum structures. Atom is subset of Cell so cell is another different bigger quantum variable than quantum structure.

(2)Theory of Science

Introduction

Every Quantum Variable at some scale has an equation when anyone combines these equations of quantum variable numbers then a quantum variable equation is formed.

Explanation

The Quantum Variable equation can be transformed to any other Quantum Variable equation. So an atom equation can be transformed to a cell equation if this happens then the need of different science subjects disappear because there is a mathematical equation for each thing which can predict properties of things and everything about it. So there is no need to study one thing properties from chemistry and its other aspects from other different subjects.

Physics and Mathematics

This Prove Physics and Mathematics as Fundamental Subjects of the Universe.

Example

Deriving equation of quantum structure quantum variable.

Forming Equation of Quantum Structure

To derive an equation of Quantum Structure, first make an equation of each Quantum Structure and combine.

Equation of Probabilistic Quantum Structure

Consider two universes at left and right of the light cone. There are two entangled spacetime in parallel universes. Consider one atom and its entangled one in parallel universe. At each entangled point of this atom there is a spacetime particle that is entangled to the spacetime particle in entangled atom's entangled point in parallel universe. (This is explained in detail in the "Physical Meaning of First Big Order Light Split" heading at the end of this Research Article.)

For Hydrogen atom

The first orbit from the nucleus of a hydrogen atom contains entangled points at which the probability position function is centered and there can be many entangled points in the first orbit so overlap in their probability positions will make electron(s) move.

The first entangled point orbit will be the most probable (MP) orbit so by probability radius function most probable orbit distance from nucleus is:

$$P(r) = r^2 |R_{10}(r)|^2 = \frac{4r^2}{a_0^3} e^{-\frac{2r}{a_0}}$$
$$r = r_{MP} = a_0 \quad (1)$$

Now there is most probable sphere by (2), put the value by (1) in (2) or probability function you get a most probable ring as:

$$|\Psi_{100}(r, \theta, \phi)|^2 = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi a_0^3}} e^{-\frac{r}{a_0}} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$
$$= \frac{1}{\pi a_0^3 e^2} \text{ as } r = r_{MP} = a_0$$
$$x_0 = 2.9 \times 10^{29} \text{ m}$$

This is distance of ring from nucleus, fit 3 axis coordinate system at nucleus and its z axis passing through entangled point present in most probable orbit ring:

$$x = x_0 \cos\theta + x_0 \sin\phi$$
$$x = 2.9 \times 10^{29} (\cos 0^\circ + \sin 90^\circ)$$
$$x = 5.8 \times 10^{29} \text{ m}$$

This is the location of an entangled point from the nucleus in the ground state of hydrogen. Bell Inequality must follow discrete assumption of Quantum Physics so yes both sin and cos can be simultaneously 1 or 0.

General Result

$$P_{n,l}(r_{MP}, \theta_{MP}, \phi_{MP}, \sigma_{MP})$$

If The above expression is expanded and then most probable values are put to make this most probable sphere a most probable ring then a generalized equation is obtained. If n entangled points and all elements electron number is generalized in this equation then a equation is obtained that describe Probabilistic Quantum Structure. Now similarly equation of trap and transition quantum structures can be obtained and when combined then Atom equation is formed. Atom equation can be called as quantum structure equation. So Quantum Variable with name Quantum Structure or Atom has equation without doubt.

Note

Other things like making this ring or circle an ellipse will be a definite task for accuracy.

(3)Physical Quantities

Physical Quantities has following types

1.MustAdd Quantities

While forming the Theory of Reality, it is necessary to consider certain factors of Reality.

(1)Evolution Factor

Things evolve with time so a Physical quantity called "Entropic Time" is needed to describe the Evolution Factor of Reality.

(2)Unification Factor

If there are multiple theories that describe Reality Theory then ,these theories must be combined by another "Physical Quantity" that will depend on the situation.

2.ShortCut Quantities

Mathematics has become so complex that it will not be easy to solve equations or remember equations.

(1)Equation Symmetry Factor

If an Equation is very long that it cannot be remembered easily then it can be remembered by remembering the symmetry of the equation that how all variables are distributed in a pattern. This Pattern is because of Physical Quantity that depends on the situation that incorporates "Equation Symmetry Factor".

(2)Simplification Factor

If there are very long calculations then in order to predict the answer without calculations another "Physical quantity" depending on the situation is considered to incorporate "Simplification Factor".

Note

Classifying Physical Quantities as:

1.Real and Imaginary

MustAdd quantities are a type of physical quantity considered under Real,Imaginary classification of Physical quantities.

2.Real and Artificial

"ShortCut Quantities" are a type of physical quantities considered under Real,Artificial Classification of Physical quantities.

(4)Prove of String Theory

Make equipotential two negative plates in x ,y and z and in the overlap box region there is a balance point where an electron will be present whose volume will be electron volume now shoot other electrons at high speeds in this volume if some pass electron will be string indeed.

(5)Conversion of Theories

Quantum Theory is limited to only Probabilistic Quantum Structure along with some explanation of other quantum structures and sometimes other quantum variables also.String Theory is also limited to this Probabilistic Quantum Structure.This Quantum Structure transforms to Relativity at bigger Quantum variables because quantum variable can describe whole scale and everything in that scale but quantum number can highlight on one aspect of that scale.

c.Discussion

Faris' First Form of Faris' Theory of Reality

(1)Faris' First Theory

Theory of Planck-Bohr Scale Science

Introduction

Every Small Quantum Variable has a Field.Higgs Field of Higgs Boson,Probabilistic Entangled Field of Spacetime particle etc.These Fields can be predicted by two methods:(1)Small Order Light splits(This is explained in Faris' Third Theory) and (2)Faris' Field Equation.

Faris' Field Equation

At every scale if I choose two quantum variable number that are exactly opposite to each other and find difference between them i will get a number(call it golden number) at every scale of quantum variable then i have to find a relation between each scale golden number which can be find out if i

know the series that goes continuously from scale to scale. This equation when evaluated at particular scale will predict the properties of quantum variable at that scale and also tell how fields transform to Grids like spacetime, Light cone at bigger scales etc (This is explained in Faris' Third Theory)

Example

If String is some scale quantum variable then I choose one stage string and zero stage string (180 degree out of phase) and all possible vibrations lie between these two strings. This Number between two strings will predict 100% accuracy of things at the same scale. If one notices that I have considered a quantitative change in two strings to describe quality of strings otherwise each string in itself is quality and there can be many strings means quantity so I have combined quality quantity and called them quantitative change or quantity-quality.

Fission Chain Reaction

A continuous fission chain reaction on any quantum variable can predict how Reality dissociates so as to get a view of fored (small quantum variable).

Example

Suppose String is formed by fusion of Planck Scale Lengths. It is entirely possible that string is formed by some other bigger or smaller scale lengths than Planck Scale lengths.

A Continuous Fission Chain Reaction on String will cause a String to dissociate into first some small scale lengths then into more small hence everytime chain reaction proceeds new Quantum Variable is obtained. This Fission Chain Reaction will proceed to $-\infty$ of Reality or possibly there is lower reality boundary.

(2) Faris' Second Theory

Theory of Faris Point Science

Introduction

The Mid of Reality is named as Logic-Reason (Math-Phy in existing science) called Faris Point. This is the region where Logic (Math in existing science) and Reason (Physics in existing Science) together exist which are the Fundamental Subjects of Reality.

The Faris Point

Logic and Reason must together exist. They cannot exist separately in Reality. Logic-Reason is not a point where nothing exist i.e. it is not simply zero because of uniform spread of science around this point but there are other

sciences in universe so this is a point of indeterminacy i.e. 0/0 whose answer can be any science.

Key Sentences

1.Logic of Things in existing science means Math(Quantity) and Physical Reason of Things in existing science called Physics(Quality).

2.Existing Science is based on Quality and Quantity which in terms of subject in the context of existing science is defined as Math-Phy.Generalized word for Math-Phy is Logic-Reason.If there are other Sciences in Reality then Logic-Reason will represent any other two fundamental subjects.

Example

If $2+2=4$ this equation gives logic (in the context of existing science in which Math is based on Quantity) that 2 and 2 things are four but if i write this as $2N+2N=4N$ this is a Logic-Reason equation (in the context of existing science in which Math-Phy is based on Quantity-Quality).It describes force is added into force but now problem is if throughout all times and in all reality there is no situation in which two forces of two newton combine then this equation is wrong there must be a "Physical Reason".

(3)Faris' Third Theory

Theory of Newton-Einstein Scale Science

Introduction

Spacetime is present in the whole Universe.Light Cone Grid is present in the whole Multiverse which is outside Universe etc.

Light Split

Light can be splitted based on different things.

Big Order Light Splits

First Big Order Light Split

The Light Split under this order form Multiverse.

i.Energy Split

When Light is splitted by different energies, an electromagnetic spectrum is formed.

ii.Interval Split

When Light is splitted by different Intervals(Spacelike,Lightlike,Timelike etc) an Interval spectrum is formed whose Physical shape is Light Cone.

Physical Meaning of First Big Order Light Split

Consider a light cone with 3 axis.In x axis of light cone there is Real and its Virtual Universe which are entangled parallel universes.Real Universe is present at positive x axis and Virtual at negative x axis.Same two sets of

parallel entangled Universes are present in y and z axis. This is view of outside of universe there are big light cones each with 6 universes but there is whole Light Cone Grid. Each Light cone x axis Real Universe is connected with next Light cone x axis virtual universe in the x axis. Each light cone y axis real universe is connected with next light cone y axis virtual universe in y axis ,same for z axis. This form a Light Cone Grid. Light Cone Grid is present in Multiverse. This is the Physical meaning of Interval Split. The Energy is spread in this light cone Grid ,this is the Physical meaning of Energy Split.

Note

This Physical Meaning will be true if bigger Quantum Variable Mathematics collide with the mathematics of Light Cone.

Second Big Order Light Split

The Light Split under this order forms Hyperverse.

i.Object Split

Physical meaning of Second Big Order Light Split

Note

- 1.It is not confirmed until now how many orders of light split are present and how many verses are there.
- 2.It is necessary that there must be some upper Reality boundary and instead of +infinity of Reality there is Verse boundary(final bigger quantum variable boundary) named as upper Reality boundary but it is possible that there is no boundary and reality continues for +infinity.
- 3.It is necessary that there must be some lower Reality boundary and instead of -infinity of Reality there is final fored boundary(final small quantum variable boundary) named as lower Reality boundary but it is possible that there is no boundary and reality continues for -infinity.
- 4.If there is no upper or lower boundary then the Mid Point of Reality is not true.

Fusion Chain Reaction

A continuous fusion chain reaction on any quantum variable can predict how Reality combines so as to get a view of the multiverse, hyperverse etc.

Example

String Fusion Chain Reaction proceed when the first atom is formed then cell then up to multiverse, hyperverse etc.

d.The Prediction

- 1.Big and Small N Order Light Splits
- 2.Fission and Fusion Chain Reaction on Quantum Variables
- 3.Proving String Theory Experiment

4.Logic-Reason or Faris Point Quantum Variable

5.String Theory and Quantum Theory describe Quantum Structure mostly that transforms to Relativity at Big Scale.

6.Science Fundamental Subjects are Math-Phy.

e.Abbreviations

1.Logic-Reason is a general word because there can be other sciences in Reality.For Existing science Logic-Reason becomes Math-Phy and to describe this Math-Phy of existing science this Math-Phy becomes Quantity-Quality.

2.Basic Science Subjects of existing or this Science are Math-Phy so words like Math-Phy and Science are alternatively used in the context of existing Science.

3.Smaller quantum variables are called Foreed or Small quantum variables or foreed quantum variables or foreed small quantum variables.Big Quantum Variables are called Verse or Big Quantum Variables or Verse quantum variables or verse big quantum variables.Mid Quantum Variable is called Faris.

4.Small Reality boundary is called lower reality boundary or small reality boundary or foreed reality boundary or foreed small reality boundary or foreed lower reality boundary.Big Reality boundary is called Big reality boundary or upper reality boundary or verse reality boundary or verse upper reality boundary or verse big reality boundary.

f.Importance

1.This Reality Theory can describe Everything in Reality even when Relativity Fails at Black hole only Black Hole Size Quantum Variable is needed and this Theory makes another prediction.

2.This Theory resolves every Problem because it tells where each Theory is located in the whole Reality and even this Theory combines all science subjects and talks on fundamental subjects to give a complete view of whole Reality.Even this theory left the place for other sciences.

g.Conclusion

This Theory is a preliminary to understand complex Reality.This Theory is not complete but will be completed early.It tries to combine all science to describe the whole Reality even if there are infinities in Reality.Although there are some Problems in this Theory but those Problems are resolved one by one in the next forms of Theory of Reality.

6.Acknowledgements

“I support the efforts of my Sirs for motivating me to study Physics.”